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Abstract

Uveal melanoma (UM) is the most common primary intraocular tumour in adults. Local resection, radiation therapy, and enucleation are the current first-line, primary UM treatments. However, regardless of the treatment received, around 50% of UM patients will develop metastatic disease within five to seven years. In the largest published series of unselected patients with metastatic UM (mUM), the median survival time after diagnosis of metastasis was 3.6 months, with less than 1% of patients surviving beyond 5 years. Approved drugs for treatment of metastatic UM (mUM) include systemic treatment with tebentafusp-tebn or isolated hepatic perfusion (IHP) with melphalan. However, these drugs are only available to a subset of patients and improve survival by only a few months, highlighting the urgent need for new mUM treatments. Accurately predicting which patients are at high risk for metastases is also crucial. Researchers are developing gene expression signatures in primary UM to create reliable prognostic models aimed at improving patient follow-up and treatment strategies. In this review we discuss the evidence supporting ferroptosis, a non-apoptotic form of cell death, as a potential novel treatment target and prognosticator for UM.

52 Uveal melanoma (UM) is the most common primary intraocular tumour in adults (Jager *et al.*, 2020).
53 The incidence of UM varies globally: Northern Europe, Western Europe, and Oceania have the highest
54 incidence (>8 per million per year), followed by North America, Eastern Europe, and Southern Europe
55 (2-7.9 per million per year), with South America, Asia and Africa having the lowest incidence (<2 per
56 million per year) (Gelmi and Jager, 2024, Singh, Turell and Topham, 2011, Virgili *et al.*, 2007, Wu *et*
57 *al.*, 2023). UM arises from melanocytes in the uvea, consisting of the pigment tissues of the iris (4%
58 of cases), the ciliary body (6% of cases), and the choroid (90% of cases) (Shields *et al.*, 2009). Risk
59 factors for UM include older age, fair skin, light eyes, inability to tan, ocular or oculodermal
60 melanocytosis, cutaneous, iris or choroidal nevi and BRCA-1 associated protein 1 (*BAP1*) mutations
61 (Jager *et al.*, 2020). Men have a higher age adjusted UM incidence (5.8 per million) compared to
62 women (4.4 per million) (Singh, Turell and Topham, 2011, Jager *et al.*, 2020). When present, UM
63 symptoms include blurred or distorted vision, visual field loss, and photopsia (Damato and Damato,
64 2012). Clinical diagnosis of UM is typically conducted using indirect ophthalmoscopy and eye slit
65 lamp biomicroscopy (Jager *et al.*, 2020). Here, we discuss current strategies for the clinical
66 management of UM (*Figure 1A*), and explore ferroptosis as a promising candidate for UM treatment
67 and prognostication (*Figure 1B, Table 1*).

68

1.1. Uveal Melanoma Clinical Management

69 Local resection, radiation therapy (including plaque radiotherapy and proton beam therapy), and
70 enucleation are the current treatments for primary UM (Yang *et al.*, 2018). However, regardless of the
71 treatment received, many patients develop metastatic UM (mUM) within five to seven years (Awh and
72 Wilson, 2020). The median survival time after diagnosis of metastasis in the largest published series
73 of unselected patients with mUM was 3.6 months, with less than 1% of patients surviving after 5 years
74 (Diener-West *et al.*, 2005). This poor prognosis significantly impacts the quality of life and mental
75 wellbeing of UM patients. UM patients with unfavourable prognoses, as determined by cytogenetic
76 testing, show increased depression and anxiety, compared to patients with favourable prognoses
77 (Rabsahl *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, UM patients with metastases have been reported to have elevated
78 anxiety and depression compared to those without metastases (Rabsahl *et al.*, 2023).

79 Common sites of metastasis include the liver, lung, bone, skin, subcutaneous tissue and the lymph
80 nodes (Diener-West *et al.*, 2005). In 2022, tebentafusp-tebn (KIMMTRAK^R) was approved by the
81 Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the European Medicines Agency (EMA), as the first disease-
82 specific treatment for mUM, but tebentafusp-tebn is restricted to HLA-A*0201 haplotypes,
83 representing 50% of patients with European ancestry (Hurley *et al.*, 2020, Chen and Carvajal, 2022,
84 Nathan *et al.*, 2021). In August 2023, the FDA approved HEPZATO KIT (melphalan for injection via
85 the hepatic delivery system) for mUM. To be eligible for melphalan patients must have unresectable
86 metastases in less than half of the liver and extrahepatic disease limited to the bone, lymph nodes,
87 subcutaneous tissues or lung that is amenable to resection or radiation (Zager *et al.*, 2022). This
88 criterion may leave patients with advanced metastatic disease unable to receive melphalan. Recently,
89 the combination of crizotinib and darovasertib showed promising results in clinical trials; however, the
90 combination has yet to receive FDA approval (Cao *et al.*, 2023).

91 Clinicians use histopathological features and genetic aberrations for UM prognosis. Poor prognostic
92 factors include large tumour size, ciliary body involvement, extra-scleral extension, the presence of
93 epithelioid cells compared to spindle cells, a high number of mitotic figures in the tumour, presence of
94 extravascular loops and networks, and vortex vein involvement (Kaliki, Shields and Shields, 2015).

95 The driver UM mutations occur in G protein subunit alpha q, G protein subunit alpha 11, cysteinyl
96 leukotriene receptor 2 or phospholipase C beta 4, which activate the G alpha q pathway (Gelmi and
97 Jager, 2024), but these mutations are typically not prognostic. A chromosomal aberration associated
98 with poor prognosis is chromosome 3 loss, leading to *BAP1* inactivation, which occurs in 84% of
99 metastasizing UMs (Harbour *et al.*, 2010). UM patients with disomy 3 have a 90% 5-year survival rate,
100 compared to 37% for patients with monosomy 3 (Versluis *et al.*, 2015). Gene expression profiling
101 (GEP) and Preferentially Expressed Antigen in Melanoma (PRAME) expression are also used for
102 prognostication, with GEP class 2 tumours and high PRAME levels indicating worse outcomes (Gelmi
103 and Jager, 2024). The Liverpool Uveal Melanoma Prognosticator Online algorithm can determine the
104 risk of metastases and estimate UM patient survival (Lamas *et al.*, 2021).

105 Epigenetic mechanisms, including DNA methylation, chromatin remodelling, histone modification,
106 and non-coding RNAs (miRNAs), also play a role in predicting prognosis for UM (Chokhachi
107 Baradaran *et al.*, 2020). One example is the Ras association domain family 1 isoform A (*RASSF1A*)
108 gene, which is often silenced through promoter hypermethylation in UM, promoting cancer
109 progression (Calipel *et al.*, 2011). Methylation of the *P16INK4A* promoter is also associated with a
110 higher risk of metastasis in UM patients (Maat *et al.*, 2008). Additionally, increased expression of
111 certain miRNAs (let-7b, miR-143, miR-193b, miR-199a, and miR-652) is linked to more aggressive
112 Class 2 UM tumours, helping distinguish them from less aggressive Class 1 tumours (Worley *et al.*,
113 2008).

114 Ongoing UM research aims to develop gene signatures to create reliable prognostic models, as no
115 universally accepted model combining clinical and molecular data currently exists.

116 **1.2. Ferroptosis Has Potential as a Novel Therapeutic Target for UM**

117 Ferroptosis is a form of cell death triggered by iron-mediated overproduction of lipid reactive oxygen
118 species (ROS). It is morphologically and biochemically distinct from autophagy, apoptosis, necrosis,
119 and necroptosis (Dixon *et al.*, 2012). Ferroptosis can be induced by inhibiting cell membrane
120 transporters such as the cystine/glutamate transporter (system X_c⁻), activating the iron transporters
121 serotransferrin and lactotransferrin, or by blocking intracellular antioxidant enzymes, such as
122 glutathione peroxidase 4 (GPX4) (Tang and Kroemer, 2020). Normally, the cystine/glutamate
123 transporter brings cystine into cells, where it is converted to cysteine, which is used to produce
124 glutathione (GSH). GPX4 uses GSH to convert polyunsaturated-fatty-acid-containing-phospholipid
125 hydroperoxide (PL-PUFA-OOH) into phospholipid alcohols, preventing PL-PUFA-OOH
126 accumulation which induces ferroptosis (Yang *et al.*, 2014, C. Zhang *et al.*, 2022). Cellular iron uptake
127 occurs through serum transferrin binding to the transferrin receptor and subsequent endocytosis. A
128 build-up of iron intracellularly generates ROS through the iron-dependent Fenton reaction, initiating
129 lipid peroxidation and thus ferroptosis (Dixon and Stockwell, 2014, C. Zhang *et al.*, 2022). Iron
130 accumulation, and consequently ferroptosis induction, can also result from the enzymatic activity of
131 heme oxygenase 1 (HO-1), which breaks down heme into carbon monoxide, biliverdin, and free iron
132 (Chiang, Chen and Chang, 2018).

133 Ferroptosis reduces metastasis in several cancers and can overcome treatment resistance (Wang *et al.*,
134 2023, C. Zhang *et al.*, 2022). Examples include cisplatin, which induces ferroptosis by inhibiting
135 system X_c⁻ and GPX4, and enhances the effects of immune checkpoint therapy in non-small cell lung
136 cancer (Zhou *et al.*, 2022). In triple-negative breast cancer, cells resistant to gefitinib become more
137 sensitive when GPX4 is inhibited, which leads to ferroptosis (Song *et al.*, 2020). In KRAS-mutant
138 metastatic colorectal cancer, combining the ferroptosis inducer β -elemene with cetuximab increases

139 sensitivity to treatment by triggering ferroptosis (Chen *et al.*, 2020). Research shows that ferroptosis
140 contributes to the death of 90-99% of circulating cancer cells, preventing them from metastasizing
141 (Groenewoud *et al.*, 2023, Piskounova *et al.*, 2015, Yagoda *et al.*, 2007). Therefore, inducing
142 ferroptosis in resistant tumours with a high propensity to metastasize, such as UM, may be beneficial.
143 Intriguingly, ferroptosis is the cell death mechanism of several anti-cancer drugs, highlighting its
144 potential (Su *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, analyses of the Tissue Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) and
145 Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) datasets show that ferroptosis-associated genes can predict UM
146 prognosis (Groenewoud *et al.*, 2023, Jin *et al.*, 2021, Luo and Ma, 2021, Ma *et al.*, 2022, Tonelotto *et*
147 *al.*, 2024, Wang *et al.*, 2022).

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149 **2. Evidence on Ferroptosis as a Promising Strategy for Uveal Melanoma Treatment and** 150 **Prognostication**

151 Recent studies have shown the effectiveness of ferroptosis in *in vitro*, *ex vivo* and *in vivo* UM models,
152 which are discussed below (Table 1, Figure 1B).

153 **2.1. In Vitro Efficacy of Ferroptosis in Uveal Melanoma**

154 Jin *et al.* proposed that decapping scavenger enzymes (DCPS) impacts ferroptosis by regulating mRNA
155 decay during UM metastasis to the liver (Fuchs *et al.*, 2020, van Dijk, Le Hir and Séraphin, 2003). This
156 hypothesis is based on the fact that DCPS regulates expression of glutaredoxins, which scavenge ROS,
157 thereby preventing ferroptosis. The group treated UM cells with RG30309, a DCPS inhibitor, which
158 resulted in an increase in ROS generation and ferroptosis induction. (Jin *et al.*, 2023).

159 Tonelotto *et al.* demonstrated the *in vitro* efficacy of ferroptosis in UM by elucidating the mechanism
160 of action of 1,4-dihydroxy quininib, a cysteinyl leukotriene receptor 1 (CysLT₁) antagonist which
161 inhibits UM hallmarks (Slater *et al.*, 2022, Slater *et al.*, 2020, Tonelotto *et al.*, 2024). The group
162 performed proteome-profiling of OMM2.5 mUM cell extracts treated with 1,4-dihydroxy quininib.
163 They found that HO-1 was consistently upregulated, with lipid hydroperoxide and ROS levels
164 increasing and GPX4 expression decreasing in a time-dependent manner. These findings indicate that
165 1,4-dihydroxy quininib reduces UM cell viability by inducing ferroptosis (Tonelotto *et al.*, 2024).
166 Treatment of OMM2.5 cells with the histone deacetylase inhibitor (HDACi) ACY-1215 or with the
167 natural product Ergolide, both of which inhibit UM hallmarks, also altered the expression of ferroptotic
168 markers ASCL3 and GCLC or HO-1 and GDF15, respectively (Sundaramurthi *et al.*, 2023,
169 Sundaramurthi *et al.*, 2022). This reinforces ferroptosis as a UM therapeutic target.

170 Wang *et al.* developed gallic acid (GA)-Fe (III) and paclitaxel (PTX)-assembled nanoparticles (FeP
171 Nps), which are internalized into tumour cells through ultrasound (US) irradiation, activating the
172 Fenton reaction and leading to ferroptosis (Wang *et al.*, 2024). FePNPs treatment reduced B16F10 cell
173 viability and increased ROS, membrane lipid peroxidation and intracellular iron levels. FePNPs also
174 inhibited solute carrier family member 7 (SLC7A11) thus suppressing GSH production, decreased
175 GPX4 levels and increased the expression of Acyl-CoA synthase long-chain family member 4
176 (ACSL4), which modulates lipid composition levels (Ding *et al.*, 2023, Wang *et al.*, 2024).
177 Furthermore, the treated cells displayed altered mitochondria (Wang *et al.*, 2024). These results
178 indicate that FeP NPs activate ferroptosis. It is important to note that B16F10 cells are melanoma cells,
179 which raises questions about this treatment's efficacy in UM.

180 Zhu *et al.* targeted the fibroblast growth factor (FGF)/FGF Receptor (FGFR) axis, which is associated
181 with poor prognosis in UM patients (Rezzola *et al.*, 2019). Erdafitinib, a pan-FGFR tyrosine kinase
182 inhibitor, reduced 92.1 and Mel202 UM cell viability (Zhu *et al.*, 2024). Additionally, Erdafitinib
183 affected content of iron, GSH and levels of malondialdehyde (MDA), a marker of lipid peroxidation,
184 thus implicating ferroptosis (Cordiano *et al.*, 2023, Zhu *et al.*, 2024).

185 Zhang *et al.* evaluated the effect of non-oxidized MXene-Ti₃C₂T_x quantum dots (NMQDs-Ti₃C₂T_x)
186 on C918 (UM) and Mum-2B (mUM) cell lines (H. Zhang *et al.*, 2022). Following treatment, cell
187 proliferation and invasiveness were reduced, and intracellular levels of ROS, MDA, and lipid peroxides
188 increased. The treatment also decreased intracellular GSH concentration and upregulated RNA levels
189 of *SLC7A11*, indicating negative feedback on GSH. Moreover, NMQDs-Ti₃C₂T_x treatment upregulated
190 mRNA levels of *PTGS2*, a ferroptosis-related gene (H. Zhang *et al.*, 2022). These findings indicate
191 that NMQDs-Ti₃C₂T_x evoke UM cell death through ferroptosis.

192 Hou *et al.* investigated the effect of small-molecule inhibitors of enhancers of zeste homolog 2,
193 including UNC 1999 and GSK126, in OMM1 mUM cells. They found that UNC 1999 and GSK126
194 suppressed OMM1 cell growth, with UNC 1999 altering the expression of ferroptosis-related genes.
195 UNC 1999 increased intracellular Fe²⁺, ROS and MDA levels, decreased GSH levels, disrupted
196 mitochondria morphology, and diminished maximal respiration and adenosine triphosphate production
197 in the mitochondria. These findings provide compelling evidence that UNC 1999 induces UM cell
198 death through ferroptosis (Hou *et al.*, 2022).

199 Groenewoud *et al.* showed that the ferroptosis inducers erastin and RSL3 reduced MM66 (mUM) and
200 Mel285 (UM) cell viability (Groenewoud *et al.*, 2023); while Dörschmann *et al.* demonstrated that
201 erastin induced OMM1 cell death, and that specific fucoidan extracts inhibited erastin effects
202 (Dörschmann *et al.*, 2021).

203 **2.2. *Ex Vivo* and *in Vivo* Efficacy of Ferroptosis in Uveal Melanoma**

204 Ferroptosis has been thoroughly investigated in *ex vivo* and *in vivo* UM models, which provide greater
205 insight into the tumour macro- and microenvironment than cell lines (Hidalgo *et al.*, 2014, Lee, Lin
206 and Tsai, 2021).

207 Jin *et al.* subcutaneously injected OMM1 cells into Non-Obese Diabetic Severe Combined Immune
208 Deficiency mice and, after three weeks, observed that the tumour volumes and weights of OMM1
209 xenografts were significantly reduced after RG3039 treatment compared to the vehicle-treated mice
210 (Jin *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, levels of 4-hydroxynonenal (4-HNE), a reactive aldehyde derived from
211 lipid peroxidation, increased after RG3039 treatment. In a separate set of mice bearing UM patient-
212 derived xenografts (PDX), RG3039 treatment similarly reduced tumour volume and weight (Jin *et al.*,
213 2023). This research supports the *in vivo* efficacy of ferroptosis in UM.

214 Tonelotto *et al.* treated tumour explants from mUM orthotopic PDX mouse models with 1,4-dihydroxy
215 quininib. The treatment led to an upregulation of HO-1 expression and to increased levels of 4-HNE,
216 suggesting that 1,4-dihydroxy quininib induces ferroptosis in patient-derived mUM explants
217 (Tonelotto *et al.*, 2024).

218 Wang *et al.* observed a near-complete disappearance of intraocular tumours in nude mice injected with
219 BF16F10-Luc melanoma cells intraocularly and treated with Fep Nps and US irradiation (Wang *et al.*,

220 2024). These results provide evidence for the anticancer efficacy of Fep Nps, which induced ferroptosis
221 *in vitro*.

222 Zhu *et al.* treated 92.1 xenograft models with Erdafitinib, which reduced lesion volume compared to
223 the control group. These results align with *in vitro* data demonstrating Erdafitinib's anticancer activity
224 through ferroptosis induction (Zhu *et al.*, 2024).

225 Zhang *et al.* found that tumor growth significantly increased in the control group compared to the
226 NMQDs-Ti₃C₂Tx-treated group in mice injected with C918 cells (H. Zhang *et al.*). This supports the
227 antitumor activity of NMQDs-Ti₃C₂Tx, which were shown to induce ferroptosis *in vitro*.

228 Groenewoud *et al.* generated patient-derived zebrafish UM xenograft models and treated them with
229 erastin and RSL3. RSL3 inhibited metastasis formation in zebrafish engrafted with UM and mUM
230 cells, all of which highly expressed GPX4. Similarly, erastin inhibited tumour burden in zebrafish
231 engrafted with UM and mUM cells (Groenewoud *et al.*, 2023), highlighting the *in vivo* efficacy of
232 ferroptosis in UM.

233 **2.3. Ferroptosis Gene Signatures as a Uveal Melanoma Prognostic Tool**

234 Ferroptosis-related gene signatures have emerged as potential biomarkers for UM, offering novel
235 insights into prognosis and treatment response.

236 Groenewoud *et al.* found that *GPX4* expression negatively correlates with survival in the Leiden
237 University Medical Centre (LUMC) UM cohort, while *SLC7A11* expression shows similar trends in
238 the TCGA-UM cohort. They also analyzed a panel of eight primary UM patient samples, which were
239 compared to a *BAP1* positive and *BAP1* negative mUM cell lines. The analysis revealed a strong
240 inverse correlation between *BAP1* and *GPX4*, implicating ferroptosis in mUM progression
241 (Groenewoud *et al.*, 2023).

242 Tonelotto *et al.* analysed data from the TCGA-UM and GSE84976 cohorts and identified a ferroptosis-
243 related gene signature (IFerr), including *GPX4*, *SCL7A11*, solute-carrier family 3 member 2 (*SLC3A2*),
244 glutamate cysteine ligase modifier (*GCLM*), cystathionine gamma-lyase (*CTH*), acyl-CoA synthetase
245 long-chain family member 3 (*ACSL3*), NAD(P)H quinone dehydrogenase 1 (*NQO1*), iron responsive
246 element binding protein 2 (*IREB2*) and apoptosis inducing factor mitochondria associated 2 (*AIFM2*).
247 High IFerr is observed in monosomy 3 patients in both databases and predicts decreased overall
248 survival (OS) and disease-free survival (DFS) in UM patients (Tonelotto *et al.*, 2024).

249 Luo *et al.* developed a ferroptosis-related gene signature including six-transmembrane epithelial
250 antigen of prostate 3 (*STEAP3*), microtubule associated protein 1 light chain 3 gamma (*MAP1LC3C*),
251 integrin subunit alpha 6 (*ITGA6*), *HO-1*, *CD44*, arachidonate 12-lipoxygenase (*ALOX12*) and
252 *AIFM2*/ferroptosis suppressor protein1 (*FSP1*) using data from TCGA-UM and GSE22138 cohorts.
253 This signature is strongly associated with UM prognosis and can precisely detect UM risk level (Luo
254 and Ma, 2021).

255 Jin *et al.* identified that the expression of ferroptosis regulators including *ABCC1*, glutathione specific
256 gamma-glutamylcyclotransferase 1 (*CHAC1*) and glutathione synthetase (*GSS*), is associated with poor
257 OS, PFS and disease-specific survival (DSS) in UM (Jin *et al.*, 2021).

258 Ma *et al.* evaluated ferroptosis-related long noncoding RNAs (FRLs) using the TGCA-UM database
259 and identified a five FRLs signature, including *AC104129.1*, *AC136475.3*, *LINC00963*,

260 *PPP1R14B.AS1* and *ZNF667.AS1*, which correlates with a shorter overall life expectancy in UM
261 patients (Ma *et al.*, 2022).

262 Wang *et al.* found significant correlations between the expression levels of transient receptor potential
263 melastatin 4 (TRPM4) and transient receptor potential vanilloid 2 (TRPV2) with OSS and DSS in the
264 TCGA-UM cohort. They also observed that expression levels of farnesyl-diphosphate
265 farnesyltransferase 1 (*FDFT1*), solute carrier family 1 member 5 (*SLCIA5*), heat shock proteins
266 (*HSPAS*), *SLC7A11* and ER membrane protein complex subunit 2 (*EMC2*), which participate in
267 ferroptosis, significantly correlate with TRPV2 and TRPM4 expression. This suggests that TRPM4
268 and TRPV2 are associated with the ferroptosis pathway in UM (Wang *et al.*, 2022).

269 **3. Current Challenges of Implementing Ferroptosis Inducers in the Clinic**

270 **3.1 Immune Implications of Ferroptosis Inducers**

271 Inducing ferroptosis as a cancer treatment presents several challenges and potential side effects that
272 must be carefully considered. One major concern is its impact on immune cells, where ferroptosis in
273 CD8+ T cells can weaken antitumor immunity, as observed in colon cancer models. This effect, though
274 mitigated by overexpressing GPX4, underscores the potential for ferroptosis to negatively affect the
275 immune response (Ma *et al.*, 2021; Xu *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, the ferroptosis inducer RSL3 impairs
276 dendritic cell function, suggesting risks to immune system integrity (Han *et al.*, 2021).

277 **3.2 Potential Side Effects of Ferroptosis Inducers**

278 Cardiovascular and neurological risks are also associated with ferroptosis. For example, reduced GPX4
279 levels and increased iron have been linked to heart disease progression and are implicated in
280 neurological conditions like hemorrhagic stroke (Baba *et al.*, 2018; Nobuta *et al.*, 2019; Zille *et al.*,
281 2017).

282 Gastrointestinal and renal complications further complicate ferroptosis treatment. For instance,
283 ferroptosis can exacerbate inflammatory bowel disease and trigger acute kidney injury when GPX4 is
284 depleted (Mayr *et al.*, 2020; Friedmann Angeli *et al.*, 2014).

285 Cancer-specific challenges also exist. In pancreatic cancer, ferroptosis can promote tumor growth by
286 influencing macrophage polarization and is linked to conditions like pancreatitis and pancreatic
287 tumorigenesis (Dai *et al.*, 2020; Liu *et al.*, 2022). It may also worsen hepatocellular carcinoma
288 development (He *et al.*, 2023).

289 Additionally, resistance to ferroptosis inducers is a potential issue, as seen in mUM cells that increase
290 GLCM expression and glutathione content to resist ferroptosis (Tonelotto *et al.*, 2024).

291 While ferroptosis holds promise as a cancer treatment, addressing these challenges, including
292 specificity, toxicity, resistance, and immune effects, is essential for its successful clinical application.
293 These obstacles could potentially be overcome by ensuring that ferroptosis inducers selectively target
294 cancer cells, minimizing damage to healthy tissues. One promising approach is the use of
295 nanotechnology to deliver ferroptosis inducers directly to tumours, enhancing specificity and reducing
296 systemic toxicity (Xiang *et al.*, 2024). Additionally, combination therapies that pair ferroptosis
297 inducers with existing treatments, like immunotherapy or chemotherapy, may help increase treatment
298 effectiveness.

304 efficacy while managing side effects (Huang *et al.*, 2023). Further research into biomarkers for
305 ferroptosis sensitivity could also allow for more personalized treatment strategies.

306

307

4. Discussion

308 Ferroptosis inducers represent a promising new approach for treating mUM, addressing the limitations
309 of current therapies. These inducers trigger a unique form of cell death that operates independently of
310 other treatment mechanisms, such as those targeted by darovasertib, a PKC inhibitor, and crizotinib, a
311 c-Met inhibitor, which have shown significant efficacy in reducing tumor size in Phase II trials (Cao
312 *et al.*, 2023). Ferroptosis inducers could thus be valuable when resistance to these targeted therapies
313 occurs. Additionally, emerging treatments like HDAC inhibitors, especially those targeting HDAC6,
314 are showing promise for mUM (Li, Tian, and Zhu, 2020; Sundaramurthi *et al.*, 2022). Combining these
315 inhibitors with ferroptosis inducers may provide a synergistic therapeutic approach. Furthermore,
316 ferroptosis inducers may offer treatment options for patients who are ineligible for current FDA-
317 approved therapies. Expanding ferroptosis inducers from preclinical success to clinical use requires
318 extensive research to assess efficacy and safety through human trials, typically a decade-long process
319 (Lee *et al.*, 2018; Rang and Hill, 2013; Sedgwick, 2011). Comparing ferroptosis inducers with existing
320 treatments is crucial to establish their therapeutic advantage.

321 In summary, ferroptosis inducers offer a novel and potentially transformative treatment for mUM,
322 complementing and possibly enhancing the current therapeutic landscape.

323

324

5. Future Perspectives

325 Overall, this review highlights the need for more translational research on ferroptosis in clinically
326 relevant UM models to bridge the gap between preclinical findings and clinical applications.

327 To translate ferroptosis inducers into clinical practice, key challenges include improving delivery to
328 tumor sites due to their limited bioavailability (Ko *et al.*, 2024). Advances in nanotechnology offer
329 promising solutions, such as biomimetic self-assembling nano-prodrugs that deliver multiple agents
330 simultaneously. Huang *et al.* demonstrated a nano-prodrug system delivering gefitinib, ferrocene, and
331 dihydroartemisinin effectively inhibiting tumor growth through combined ferroptosis and apoptosis
332 therapy (Huang *et al.*, 2023). This underscores the potential of such delivery systems and drug
333 combinations in optimizing ferroptosis-based treatments for UM.

334 Ongoing translational research using clinically relevant UM models is essential for linking preclinical
335 findings to real-world applications, ensuring that ferroptosis can be effectively integrated into the
336 broader cancer treatment landscape.

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340

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345 **Conflict of Interest**

346 BNK and VT are named inventors on a filed patent application related to UM biomarkers.

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593 **Figure 1. Current clinical management of uveal melanoma and evidence on ferroptosis as**
594 **potential treatment and prognosticator for the disease. (A)** Uveal melanoma (UM) is the most
595 common intraocular malignancy in adults, originating from melanocytes in the uveal tract (choroid,
596 ciliary body, iris). The primary disease is typically treated with radiotherapy, which uses high-energy
597 x-rays to kill cancer cells; brachytherapy, where a plaque with radioactive sources is surgically
598 implanted on the sclera overlying the tumor; or enucleation, in which the eye is removed if the tumor
599 is too large for vision-sparing treatments. Despite these treatments, hematogenous spread of UM cells
600 leads to metastasis in up to half of all patients, usually within a median time of approximately three
601 years. Nearly 90% of metastases occur in the liver. Histopathological features and DNA/RNA-based
602 tests (e.g., chromosome 3 status, gene expression analysis) can predict progression to metastatic
603 disease. However, these assays often require biopsies in patients not undergoing enucleation. Biopsies
604 are highly invasive, carry a risk of vision-threatening complications, and are limited by sampling
605 variability. Therapeutic options for metastatic UM are limited and include immunotherapy and liver-
606 directed therapies. Only two FDA-approved treatments, Tebentafusp-tebn and melphalan/HDS, are
607 available for metastatic UM, and these only moderately prolong survival (Jager et al., 2020, Nathan et
608 al., 2021, Zager et al., 2022). Tebentafusp, which is administered intravenously, is a bispecific fusion
609 protein with two key components: one binds specifically to the gp100 antigen on UM cells, while the
610 second attaches to cluster of differentiation 3 (CD3), a receptor on T cells. This connection activates
611 the T cells, redirecting them to attack the tumor cells. gp100, glycoprotein 100; HLA-A, human
612 leucocyte antigen-A; TCR, T cell receptor. The melphalan/HDS is a chemotherapy drug/device
613 combination used for liver-directed treatment of mUM patients (Zager et al., 2022). **(B)** Ferroptosis
614 has emerged as a new player in anticancer therapies. Three main pathways regulate the process of
615 ferroptosis: the canonical GPX4-regulated pathway, the lipid metabolism pathway and the iron
616 metabolism pathway. Key components include system X_c⁻: cystine/glutamate antiporter; GSH:
617 glutathione; GPX4: glutathione peroxidase 4; GS-SG: glutathione disulfide; GR: glutathione reductase;
618 NADPH: nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate; PUFA: polyunsaturated fatty acid; ACSL4:
619 acyl-CoA synthetase long chain family member 4; CoA: coenzyme A; LPCAT3:
620 lysophosphatidylcholine acyltransferase 3; PL: phospholipid; LOX: lipoxygenases; POR: cytochrome
621 P450 oxidoreductase; PL-PUFA-OOH: PUFA-containing-phospholipid hydroperoxides; PL-PUFA-
622 OH: PUFA-containing- phospholipid alcohols; ROS: reactive oxygen species; Fe³⁺: ferric ion; Fe²⁺:
623 ferrous ion; H₂O₂: hydrogen peroxide; HO-1: heme oxygenase (C. Zhang et al., 2022). Studies have
624 demonstrated the potential of ferroptosis as a therapeutic target in UM through various treatments *in*
625 *vitro* (Erastin, RSL3, RG3039, 1,4-dihydroxy quininib, Fep Nps, Erdafitinib, NMQDs-Ti3C2Tx,
626 UNC1999); *ex vivo* (1,4-dihydroxy quininib); and *in vivo* (RG3039, Fep Nps, Erdafitinib, NMQDs-
627 Ti3C2Tx in mouse UM models; Erastin and RSL3 in zebrafish UM models). Ferroptosis-related
628 signatures including *GPX4*, *SCL7A11*, *SLC3A2*, *HMOX1*, *GCLM*, *CTH*, *NQO1*, *ACSL3*, *IREB2*, *POR*,
629 *AIFM2*, *STEAP3*, *MAP1LC3C*, *ITGA6*, *CD44*, *ALOX12*, *ABCC1*, *CHAC1*, *GSS*, *AC104129.1*,
630 *AC136475.3*, *LINC00963*, *PPP1R14B.AS1*, and *ZNF667.AS1* appear to be good candidate to predict
631 disease progression and response to therapies (Dörschmann et al., 2021, Groenewoud et al., 2023, Hou
632 et al., 2022, Jin et al., 2023, Tonelotto et al., 2024, Wang et al., 2024, H. Zhang et al., 2022, Zhu et al.,
633 2024). Created with BioRender.com. Subscription: Institution (University College Dublin).

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638 **Table 1.** List of the *in vitro*, *ex vivo* and *in vivo* studies conducted on ferroptosis in uveal melanoma.

Drug	Role in Ferroptosis Induction	<i>In vitro</i> , <i>ex vivo</i> or <i>in vivo</i> testing	Results	References
RG30309	DCPS inhibition induces GLRX-mediated ROS production, leading to the formation of lipid peroxides	<i>In vitro</i> : UM 92.1 (primary), Mel270 (primary), OMM1 (metastatic), OMM2.3 (metastatic) and MP41 (primary) cells <i>In vivo</i> : NOD/SCID mice injected subcutaneously with OMM1 cells	RG30309 impedes UM cell growth <i>in vitro</i> through ferroptosis and diminishes hepatic metastasis of UM cells <i>in vivo</i>	(Jin <i>et al.</i> , 2023)
1,4-dihydroxy quininib	- Increases ROS, HO-1 expression and lipid hydroxide levels - Decreases GPX4 expression and affects GSH content - Modulates the expression of ferroptosis-related proteins including SLC3A2, GCLM, CTH, ACSL3, NQO1, IREB2 and AIFM2	<i>In vitro</i> : UM OMM2.5 (metastatic) and Mel285 (primary) cells <i>Ex vivo</i> : Metastatic UM OPDX	1,4-dihydroxy quininib induces UM cell death through ferroptosis <i>in vitro</i> and increases ferroptotic markers levels <i>ex vivo</i>	(Toneletto <i>et al.</i> , 2024)
Gallic acid (GA)-Fe (III) and paclitaxel (PTX)-assembled nanoparticles (Fep Nps)	- Increases ROS, membrane lipid peroxidation and intracellular iron levels. - Suppresses intracellular GSH production by inhibiting system Xc-activation - Decreases GPX4 expression and increased ACSL4 levels	<i>In vitro</i> : B16F10 cells (from mouse melanoma) <i>In vivo</i> : Nude mice injected with B16F10-Luc melanoma cells intraocularly in the right eye	FepNps reduce melanoma cells growth <i>in vitro</i> by ferroptosis induction and inhibits tumor growth and metastasis <i>in vivo</i>	(Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2024).
Erdafitinib	- Affects iron, GSH and MDA levels - Enhances the transcriptional activity of TFEB, whose aggregation in the nucleus triggers FTH1-dependent ferritinophagy, leading to lysosomal activation	<i>In vitro</i> : UM 921.1 (primary) and Mel202 (primary) cells <i>In vivo</i> : UM 92.1 xenograft models	Erdafitinib induces UM cell death by promoting ferroptosis <i>in vitro</i> and suppresses tumor growth <i>in vivo</i>	(Zhu <i>et al.</i> , 2024)
NMQDs-Ti₃C₂Tx	- Increases ROS, MDA and lipid peroxide levels. - Decreases GSH concentration and increases <i>SLC7A11</i> levels - Upregulates <i>PTGS2</i> levels - Induces mitophagy and lysosome destruction	<i>In vitro</i> : UM C918 (primary) and Mum-2B (metastatic) cells <i>In vivo</i> : Mice injected with UM C918 cells	NMQDs-Ti ₃ C ₂ Tx evokes ferroptosis in UM cells <i>in vitro</i> and prevents UM xenograft tumor growth <i>in vivo</i>	(H. Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2022)
UNC 1999	- Increases intracellular iron, ROS and MDA levels; decreases GSH levels - Modulates expression of genes involved in ferroptosis pathways including <i>HMOX1</i> , <i>NRF2</i> , <i>TXNIP</i> , <i>FTH1</i> , <i>SQSTM1</i> and <i>KEAP1</i> - Causes structural damage and dysfunction in mitochondria	<i>In vitro</i> : UM OMM1 cells (metastatic)	UNC 1999 suppresses UM cell growth <i>in vitro</i> through ferroptosis	(Hou <i>et al.</i> , 2022)
Erastin and RSL3	- Erastin: SCL7A11 inhibitor - RSL3: GPX4 inhibitor	<i>In vitro</i> : UM MM66 (metastatic) and Mel285 (primary) cells <i>In vivo</i> : Patient-derived zebrafish xenografts of primary and metastatic UM	Erastin and RSL3 reduces UM cell growth <i>in vitro</i> and diminishes metastasis formation <i>in vivo</i>	(Groenewoud <i>et al.</i> , 2023)
Erastin	Decreases GPX4 expression	<i>In vitro</i> : UM OMM1 (metastatic) cells	Erastin induces UM cell death <i>in vitro</i> , which can be rescued by specific fucoidan extracts	(Dörschmann <i>et al.</i> , 2021)

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